

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

BOOK REVIEW: ERIK JAN ZURCHER'S "THE HISTORY OF MODERNIZING TURKEY"

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Abstract

In this study, E.J.Zucher's book "The History of Modernizing Turkey" summarized information about the book is mentioned. Before starting the information, it gives brief information about the author. is beneficial. There are many scientific studies on the history of Turkey in the recent period. E.J.Zücher actually specialized in the field of Turkology is a scientist. In his general studies, he is interested in Turkish politics and evaluation. E.J.Zucher, who made historical researches by doing. Also, he mentioned its quality. This book also covers the period of political parties in detail. Açar sözlər: açar söz-1, açar söz-2, açar söz-3

Keywords: E.J.Zücher, Ottoman Period, Republic Perid, Turkey History

INTRODUCTION

Erik Jan Zurcher's book, which deals with the history of Turkey since the 1800s as an original modernization process, is being taught as a textbook at major universities in Europe and the USA. Prof. Dr.-who has previously carried out important research on the founding period of the Republic of Turkey, is a faculty member of the universities of Amsterdam and Nijmegen, and also heads the Department of Turkey at the International Institute of Social History.

Zurcher deals with all the dimensions of the modernization problem in Turkey with a phenomenon that cannot be expected from a textbook, with in-depth diagnoses and a simple narrative. In the new revised edition of this case study, you will encounter different information offered by a competent historian and a fresh approach. The work is quite comprehensive and in-depth, with its straightforward narrative, it leans on social and economic history and currents of thought as well as on political events.

The author, who wrote his book with his views, titled 'Turkey, A Modern History ' and its translation into Turkey Turkish was published later, for the first time. It was made by Mete Tuncay (later Yasemin Saner), The translated version consists of 523 pages. Written as a monograph this book is about the spread of the modernization started in Europe to the Ottoman Empire. Contains in itself. In general, the author is the author of the XVIII.

The modernization started in the Ottoman Empire chronologically and finalized it in 2014.

This book is important the fact that it is still seen as a classroom in the universities of developed countries today. Although the author wrote about the modernization process with its good aspects, he also made criticisms. In the first part of the book, the author, who wrote the book as a turning point in Ottoman history, touched upon the Ottoman society and state life in the nineteenth year and stated the influence of France on modernization. Rather, he underlined the impact of the transformation of mercantilism into capitalism, which

emerged in the social life of European states, on the Ottoman Empire.

Another issue is the effect of the Congress of Vienna on the Ottoman Empire, which led to the emergence of movements such as nationalism and nationalism in political and social life. The author mentions the indebtedness of the state as a result of Britain's hegemony over the Ottoman Empire, states that France was also a process that caused a cultural change in this context, and states that the changes in law, education, finance, trade, administrative management, etc. with the Tanzimat Edict signed in 1839 were not welcomed by the religious segments in the palace life.

On the other hand, he characterized the years 1870-1908 as a period of economic and financial difficulties and in this context, he praised the beginning of the Constitutional Monarchy Period (1908). With the declaration of the Constitutional Monarchy, he mentioned the reappearance of the nationalist and conservative groups in the palace and administrative structure. He concluded this part of the book by showing the Young Turks established in France as the biggest example. In the second part of the aforementioned book, the author has described it under the title "Young Turk Period in Turkish History, 1908-1950" and chronologically evaluated the history that existed until 1950.

He described these years as the era of the rebirth of nationalism and the military taking part in the state administration, but with a change of direction, he tried to explain 1918 as the de facto collapse of the Ottoman Empire and 1923 as the beginning of the Republican Period. In this context, he mentioned that in 1918, the nationalist movement of the ' Committee of Union and Progress' changed direction with the Kemalist movement, and then changed to the Republican People's Party, and as a result of this, the arrival of the single-party government period; modernization or reforms aimed at secularization. However, the author also considered the beginning of the one-party rule period with the Takrir-i Sukûn Law in 1925 as a dictatorship.

The third part of the book is entitled 'An Uneasy Democracy' by Zucher and tries to explain the process from 1950 to the 1990s. In this context, the author, who foreshadowed the arrival of the multi-party era, mentioned the three military coups in 1960, 1971 and 1980, describing them as an uneasy period. On the other hand, the third part of the book is entitled 'The Third Republic : Turkey from 1980 to Today ', which he labelled as the periods of the Kenan Evren Coup State and Turgut Özal Economy, the Depression Years (1994 -2002), and the Justice and Development Party (2002-2014).

He described 2002-2014 as the period of return to religious and spiritual values. In 1950, the Democrat Party government continued to rule until 1960 and the author described the period of power as a period of globalization, walking in unity with the world, democratization, as well as a period of Turkey returning to religious values, national and spiritual values, and the period from the arrival of the 1960 coup until 1980, the arrival of different right and left parties, that is, a multi-party ideological Second Period. Although he states that imports and industry normalized in the economy, he criticizes all three coups as having had a negative impact on the Republic of Turkey, and in this context, he shows that the texts of the Constitution were changed and argues that this had negative consequences for a democratic country.

In the book, the author has made use of the works of a number of Turkish scholars, such as retired Prof. Zafer Toprak's 'National Economy', which he has used as a source of reference. Biographical materials were also used in the book. Namely, in this book, Ahmet

Cevdet, Abdülhamit II, Kara Vasıf, Recep Peker, Nihat Atsız, Adnan Menderes, Ahmet Rıza, Dr. Abdullah Cevdet, Turgut Özal, Ziya Gökalp, Enver Pasha, Telcin Alp, Fethi Bey, Kara Vasıf, Hacı Osman Sabancı, Erdal İnönü, Necmettin Erbakan, Turgut Özal and a number of personalities.

SUMMARY

In the book, while the reflection of external factors and the modernization that has started in the world on Ottoman life is mentioned, it is stated that domestic politics also played a role in this modernization in the Republican Period, but the coups negatively affected democratization as a result of the change of constitutional texts in the country's life. The author, who, so to speak, divided modernization into two forms, described it as traditionalists and reactionaries, and tried to interpret how traditionalists and reactionaries came to power from time to time and how much this affected modernization.

In a way, the book focuses on political life issues. Although there is not much information about the development of culture, civilization and literature, it is written as a chronological examination of how modernization came to the Ottoman and Republican Period, the process from the XVIII century to 1990, and the interpretation of the process from 1990 to 2014.

References:

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